

FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association

D2 - Exemplary standardised metadata templates for Geo-Bio samples (vegetation, water, sediment, rock samples) for all use cases (AWI, GFZ)

Authors

Mareike Wieczorek (AWI)

Birgit Heim (AWI)

Alexander Brauser (GFZ)

Kirsten Elger (GFZ)

Linda Baldewein (Hereon)

Publication Date: August 31st, 2022

Table of contents

1. Introduction	3
1.1 Purpose of this document	3
1.2 Components of this deliverable	3
2. The FAIR WISH IGSN Metadata Schema	4
2.1 Metadata Template	4
2.2 Hierarchical samples	7
3. How to use the template	8
3.1 Description of sheet “Guide”	8
3.2 Description of sheet “Template”	9
4. Discussion	9
5. References	10
6. Appendix	10
6.1 List of acronyms	10

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This document describes the deliverable D2 “*Exemplary standardised metadata templates for Geo-Bio samples (vegetation, water, sediment, rock samples) for all use cases*” of the project **FAIR Workflows** to establish IGSN for **S**amples in the **H**elmholtz Association (FAIR WISH) funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). Deliverable D2 is part of work package 3 “*Domain-specific metadata for terrestrial and aquatic Geo-Bio samples (vegetation, sediment, water, rocks)*”.

The template presents the suggested metadata elements for sample descriptions of different sample types relevant in the FAIR WISH context and shall serve as the basis for batch uploading sample-metadata to the IGSN server. The modular template was developed as an all-in-one solution for the varying use cases, with the ability for users to select only the variables needed for their specific sample type. This template can already serve for the description of individual samples and will be further developed for hierarchical sample structures later during the project (i.e. vegetation plot > soil pit > soil horizon > soil sample).

1.2 Components of this deliverable

The FAIR WISH Deliverable D2 “*Exemplary standardised metadata templates for Geo-Bio samples (vegetation, water, sediment, rock samples) for all use cases*” includes this documentation and the Excel Template for IGSN metadata generation. The Excel Template has the following two spreadsheets:

- (1) a “**Guide**” describing the full metadata schema with the option to select specific metadata fields suitable for the description of different sample types (please note that the template is prefilled for the examples provided in)
- (2) the “**Template**” spreadsheet: here we provide example descriptions of different samples: a sediment core from a lake, a soil core, a rock sample, a plant, a water sample and a core from an ICDP drilling project that is already assigned with an IGSN.
- (3) nine additional tables with controlled vocabulary describing sample types, material, classification (rock, mineral, biology), methods, landform, biome and water body. Additional links to externally managed controlled vocabulary lists are provided in the “Content” column of the “Guide”

2. The FAIR WISH IGSN Metadata Schema

IGSN's modular metadata was initially aligned with an earlier version of the DataCite Metadata Schema. It includes a mandatory registration schema with very few fields, a core descriptive schema with basic characteristics of samples and collections, and the option for allocating agents to further add disciplinary metadata fields for 'their' communities (Klump et al., 2021). At GFZ, these additions were mainly added in the framework of ICDP scientific drilling projects (Conze et al., 2017) and critical zone observatories of the DFG Priority Programme SPP 1803 "EarthShape"

The development of the FAIR WISH metadata schema is framed by

- (1) the **GFZ version of the IGSN metadata schema** already in use for their sample registration services
- (2) the identification and **integration of potential DataCite metadata fields** relevant to implement the FAIR principles in the IGSN metadata schema that have not been available at the initial development of the IGSN metadata schema (e.g. the use of PIDs, like ORCID, ROR, DOI of related literature and data, etc.). This enrichment of the actual IGSN metadata schema will be especially relevant with the upcoming merge of IGSN with DataCite and enables the provision of richer metadata beyond the few mandatory fields of the DataCite Schema.
- (3) **new fields enabling the description of new sample types** (water, vegetation, soil) from FAIR WISH use cases. These include fields for the Biome or the soil horizon, but also the possibility to provide the time and time zone for, e.g., sequentially collected water samples. A full overview of the new metadata fields is provided in Table 2.1.

2.1 Metadata Template

The System for Earth Sample Registration (SESAR, <https://www.geosamples.org/about>) offers their users webservice to customise a sample description template for batch-upload of IGSN metadata. We used this idea as inspiration and created an initial template version for FAIR WISH that can be used by researchers to provide sample metadata. In addition to the mandatory fields (required for the registration of future DataCite "DOI IGSNs¹"), users can select fields from the template that are relevant to describe their samples and create customised sample description tables. The resulting sample description tables are easier to

¹ IGSN and DataCite are currently establishing a partnership. This includes the transition of IGSN Handle Identifier to DataCite DOIs and the mapping of IGSN metadata to the DataCite metadata schema. Future IGSNs will be registered as DataCite DOIs with the resourceTypeGeneral. Each allocating agent will use a separate DOI prefix. The brand IGSN will persist.

fill by the researcher than tables that provide the full metadata schema. This is aimed as an additional incentive for the researcher and supports standardised sample descriptions.

The template was developed as Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and will be the source for semi-automated generation of standardised XML files required for the IGSN registration and IGSN landing pages. This template strategy was explicitly followed to meet the practice of researchers who mainly organise their sample descriptions in tables. Furthermore, as often information for 100 and more samples are to be registered, submitting information via bulk uploads is favoured compared to submitting information for each sample individually via a webform. We develop the template for Excel, as this is widely used in the community. It will further be possible to work with the template with Open Source programs, like Libre Office or organise the information as ASCII csv files.

The template includes a “Guide” which describes all available fields and additionally enables the selection of those variables which are necessary to describe one’s sample data. For this deliverable, we provide the full metadata schema, including the metadata fields and (sub)properties required for the IGSN registration schema (that will be provided by the allocating agent) and metadata fields that can be derived automatically and do not need to be provided by the users (e.g. the ROR identifier that will be included via an API). In addition, we adjusted the field names for the user template [column “Variable (Column name)” in the “Guide”] so that they are understandable by researchers and more intuitive than the original metadata field names in the IGSN metadata schema.

Table 2.1 Overview of added variable fields

Variable Name	Definition	Purpose/ Example
Parent identifier type	Identifier type of the sample’s parent	Defines if the parent is identified via IGSN or via sample name (sub-property of Parent Identifier)
Rock material classification	Classification specific to rock material with controlled vocabulary	
Mineral material classification	Classification specific to mineral material with controlled vocabulary	Extension of the IGSN field “classification”, to allow users to quickly identified the needed vocabulary from different vocabularies
Biological material classification	Classification specific to biological material with controlled vocabulary	

Variable Name	Definition	Purpose/ Example
Species classification	Given Species name of sampled biological material	Completely new variable to identify sampled species
Time zone	Time Zone of given sampling date-time	Necessary to correctly define the time zone in case the sampling time is given (for sequential sampling series, e.g. water samples)
Soil horizon	Soil Horizon the sample was taken in	Specifies the soil horizon of samples taken from soil
Northing / Hochwert end	End value of Northing/Hochwert	Necessary if coordinates are given as Northing/Easting (UTM) or Hochwert/Rechtswert (Gauss Krueger) and when samples were collected along e.g. a transect Although the main focus is on geographic coordinates (latitude, longitude) the addition of these fields enable the provision of coordinates from the UTM or Gauss Krueger System that are commonly used during field work
Easting / Rechtswert end	End value of Easting / Rechtswert	
Zone	UTM or Gauss Krueger zone	
Landform	Name of the landform the sample was collected in	E.g. basin, mountain, plain (extension of the location type)
Biome	Name of the biome, the sample was taken in	E.g. Boreal Forest (extension of the location type)
Water body	Type of water body if sample is taken from a lake, river etc	E.g. glacial lake, thermokarst lake (extension of the location type)
ORCID	Researchers ORCID	Extension of the “collector” field. Syntax: 0000-0001-5140-8602 (according to the DataCite Schema Version 4.4 ² , the addition of the schemeURI (https://orcid.org) is required. This will be automatically added by the allocating agent
ROR	ROR of Institute	Extension of the “affiliation” field. Syntax: “ https://ror.org/032e6b942 ” (according to the DataCite Schema Version 4.4 ³ , the ROR identifier shall be provided as https link)
Sample access	How can other people access the sample	Addition of controlled values with „destroyed“

² <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/>

³ <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/>

The internal organisation of the template is also modular and categorised by topic: In total, the template comprises 105 variables, which are divided into the seven topics (number of metadata fields given in breaks)

- “Sample” (n=20)
- “Sampling” (n=18),
- “Location” (n=25),
- “Persons/ Institutions involved” (n=15),
- “Archive” (n=5),
- “Reference” (n=9)
- “Registration” (n= 13) - not visible for the users

As some variables are specific for one material type, e.g. “horizon” for soil samples or “species” for biological samples, our next step will be to develop pre-customised template suggestions for the different sample types. Like this, we can provide the community with clear and easy to use templates for sample descriptions.

2.2 Hierarchical samples

A major advantage of the IGSN concept is the ability to link samples across different hierarchies, for example, from a lake to a core to a core section and to a core sample (Figure 2.1). This is enabled by the field “parent” in the IGSN Description Template. In our example, the core is the parent of the core section and the lake the parent of the core.

In addition to this initial and complete template that can already be used for the description of individual samples, we will create “Sub-Templates” for common Geo-Bio sample- and subsample-types with underlying hierarchies (e.g. Figure 2.1), e.g. for the use case sediment core samples from lake sediment, we will provide hierarchically structured templates to describe

- (i) lakes (as sampling feature which is described by its locality, geographic coordinates elevation and environmental variables),
- (ii) one to describe sediment cores (with its specific coordinates, linked expedition, expedition PI, sampling date, and methods) and
- (iii) core sections and (iv) samples (that likely only provide very few additional information, like sample name and sampling depth within the core).

Similar to the customised template related to this deliverable, the templates for hierarchical samples shall be user-directed and don’t require the provision of information that can be inherited from the description of elements in the higher hierarchy.

Before final publication, all template types will be distributed and discussed with users during workshops.

Figure 2.1 Example of the registration hierarchy of lake, sediment cores, core sections, and samples.

3. How to use the template

The Excel template consists of two main sheets:

- i) a Guide in which the user finds an overview of the full metadata schema (including definitions and examples to describe a sample and the original field names of the IGSN metadata schema) - and with the possibility to select only those variables needed to describe a sample
- ii) the Template itself in which only the selected variables are shown and can then be filled with metadata by the user.

All following spreadsheets are providing the controlled vocabulary to be used in different metadata fields. The column “Content” in the “Guide” spreadsheet includes links to these lists.

3.1 Description of sheet “Guide”

- In the column “Select”, add an x to all variables needed to describe your samples.
- Mandatory variables are outlined in the column named “Mandatory”.
- “Variable (Column name)” includes the names of all possible variables to be selectable by the user. Additional fields are not visible for the user, but will be added by the allocating agent.

- In “Definition”, the variables are defined and further information, e.g. on controlled vocabularies are given in the “Comment” and ‘Additional Information’ columns.
- The column “Example” provides examples on how to fill the fields.

3.2 Description of sheet “Template”

The template will be filled with columns selected in the “Guide”. To fill it with metadata, users have to make sure to follow the description and use only controlled vocabulary terms wherever they are defined. Furthermore, only one hierarchical level per table should be given, to make sure to correctly connect parents and children. In the future, the metadata for hierarchical samples can be presented as separate spreadsheets in one Excel file.

To connect parent and child levels, the child always needs the information of either the IGSN or the sample name of its parent. So, coming back to the example from Fig. 2.1, the lake has no parent, the core has the lake as parent, the core section has the core as parent and so on.

The hierarchical sample structure of some samples leads to the effect that a child (e.g. a core) may or may not have different geographic coordinates than its parent (e.g. the lake). In the example of Figure 2.1, the lake’s coordinates are mostly provided as coordinate pair of the lake’s midpoint in the first metadata table describing the lake. While the subsequent sediment core, drilled in the southern part of the lake, will have different coordinates than the lake, the core sections and core samples inherit the coordinates from the core. The resulting metadata template will consist of four data tables (lake, core, core section, core sample) of which the first two have selected the “coordinates” fields, while these are absent in the tables for core section and core sample.

4. Discussion

This template is the very first version and is applicable to individual samples of one hierarchical level only (see “Example” spreadsheet in the template). This template and templates for use cases with more hierarchies (e.g. Fig. 2.1) will be developed later in the project and discussed and adapted during the planned user workshops.

For the moment, metadata for individual samples can be written into the template. As a later step, the template serves as the basis for the software development of the batch upload as a functional extension of the IGSN registration of GFZ Data Services and the associated metadata schema optimisation and adaptation of the IGSN catalogue. Furthermore, while at the moment users have to check themselves that they fill the fields in the right format or only

the controlled vocabularies, in the future the template in Excel format should have restricted input possibilities, so that the users get a warning if their input does not fit to the field.

5. References

Klump, J., Lehnert, K., Ulbricht, D., Devaraju, A., Elger, K., Fleischer, D., Ramdeen, S., Wyborn, L. (2021): Towards Globally Unique Identification of Physical Samples: Governance and Technical Implementation of the IGSN Global Sample Number. - Data Science Journal, 20, 1, 1-16, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2021-033>

Conze, R., Lorenz, H., Ulbricht, D., Elger, K., Gorgas, T. (2017): Utilizing the International Geo Sample Number Concept in Continental Scientific Drilling During ICDP Expedition COSC-1. - Data Science Journal, 16, 1, 1-8, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-002>

6. Appendix

6.1 List of acronyms

AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research
FAIR	Guiding Principles for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable research data (Wilkinson et al., 2015)
FAIR WISH	FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association
GFZ	German Research Centre for Geosciences
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number
SESAR	System for Earth Sample Registration